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European Law Outside its Borders: Differentiated Disintegration in Northern Ireland, Gibraltar and Cyprus

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Abstract

The withdrawal of the United Kingdom from the European Union triggered a rare but significant phenomenon in European integration: differentiated disintegration. Differentiated disintegration is a process of unequal reduction in the level, scope, or membership of the EU¹. In legal terms, the application of EU law in the UK has been progressively reduced to the retention of some provisions that are applied outside the EU borders. A special case of extraterritorial application of EU Law concerns Northern Ireland (NI), Gibraltar (GIB), and the UK's Sovereign Base Areas (SBAs) in Cyprus (CY). These three territories have been affected by a conflict and share a legacy with the United Kingdom. For these reasons, the EU and the UK adopted three special Protocols attached to the UK's Withdrawal Agreement (WA), respectively, on NI, GIB, and CY. The article addresses the following **research question**: *'What are the implications of implementing the UK's Withdrawal Agreement Protocols for European differentiated disintegration?'*. This analysis disentangles the concepts of differentiated integration and differentiated disintegration from both a political and legal point of view. The first part of the article presents the conceptual framework. On the one hand, it frames the concepts of differentiated integration - internal and external - and differentiated disintegration and their differences. On the other hand, it analyzes Brexit as a phenomenon and the peculiarities of British Euroscepticism. The second section traces the UK's membership in the EU, as a history of differentiation. The scope is to frame the United Kingdom's participation in the EU as a parable going from internal differentiated integration to external differentiated disintegration. The legal analysis of the opt-outs granted to the UK will be accompanied by the political context. This article divides the UK's membership into the EU in three phases. The first phase regards internal differentiated integration, and it goes from 1973, accession year, until February 2016. This section presents the opt-outs granted to the UK and PM Cameron attempt to negotiate a 'new membership' to obtain more differentiation as a Member State. The second phase goes from 2016 till 2020 and coincides with the Brexit negotiations and the transition period. This article argues that this phase is an expression of internal differentiated disintegration, as the UK was still a Member State. Once Art.

¹ Franz Schimmelfennig and Thomas Winzen, *Ever Looser Union? Differentiated European Integration* (OUP 2022) 137–155.

50 TEU was activated, and the UK refused the possibility to revoke the withdrawal notification, the intention of leaving the EU was clear and the decision was final. The last phase coincides with the post-Brexit era, showing the first example of European external differentiated disintegration. The scope is to show how the UK's membership moved from internal differentiated integration to internal differentiated disintegration, till external differentiated disintegration with the consequent diminishing of EU Law application. The third section focuses on extraterritorial application of EU Law in the three contested countries of Northern Ireland, Gibraltar and the UK's SBAs in Cyprus. It shows what is left of EU Law after the disintegration phase. It argues that the residual application of European Law in these three contested territories is strictly linked to the role of the EU as a peacekeeper. The paper concludes with the implications of the Protocols' enforcement on European differentiated disintegration.

Keywords

Differentiated Integration – Extraterritorial Application of EU Law - Brexit – Northern Ireland – Gibraltar – Cyprus

1. Introduction

The withdrawal of the United Kingdom from the European Union triggered a rare but significant phenomenon in European integration: differentiated disintegration. Differentiated disintegration is a process of unequal reduction in the level, scope, or membership of the EU². In legal terms, the application of EU law in the UK has been progressively reduced to the retention of some provisions that are applied outside the EU borders. A special case of extraterritorial application of EU Law concerns Northern Ireland (NI), Gibraltar (GIB), and the UK's Sovereign Base Areas (SBAs) in Cyprus (CY). These three territories have been affected by a conflict and share a legacy with the United Kingdom. For these reasons, the EU and the UK adopted three special Protocols attached to the UK's Withdrawal Agreement (WA), respectively, on NI, GIB, and CY. The article addresses the following **research question**: *'What are the implications of implementing the UK's Withdrawal Agreement Protocols for European differentiated disintegration?'*. This analysis disentangles the concepts of differentiated integration and differentiated disintegration from both a political and legal point of view. The first part of the article presents the conceptual framework. On the one hand, it frames the concepts of differentiated integration - internal and external - and differentiated disintegration and their differences. On the other hand, it analyzes Brexit as a phenomenon and the peculiarities of British Euroscepticism. The second section traces the UK's membership in the EU, as a history of differentiation. The scope is to frame the United Kingdom's participation in the EU as a parable going from internal differentiated integration to external differentiated disintegration. The legal analysis of the opt-outs granted to the UK will be accompanied by the political context. This article divides the UK's membership into the EU in three phases. The first phase regards internal differentiated integration, and it goes from 1973, accession year, until February 2016. This section presents the opt-outs granted to the UK and PM Cameron attempt to negotiate a 'new membership' to obtain more differentiation as a Member State. The second phase goes from 2016 till 2020 and coincides with the Brexit negotiations and the transition period. This article argues that this phase is

² Franz Schimmelfennig and Thomas Winzen, *Ever Looser Union? Differentiated European Integration* (OUP 2022) 137–155.

an expression of internal differentiated disintegration, as the UK was still a Member State. Once Art. 50 TEU was activated, and the UK refused the possibility to revoke the withdrawal notification, the intention of leaving the EU was clear and the decision was final. The last phase coincides with the post-Brexit era, showing the first example of European external differentiated disintegration. The scope is to show how the UK's membership moved from internal differentiated integration to internal differentiated disintegration, till external differentiated disintegration with the consequent diminishing of EU Law application. The third section focuses on extraterritorial application of EU Law in the three contested countries of Northern Ireland, Gibraltar and the UK's SBAs in Cyprus. It shows what is left of EU Law after the disintegration phase. It argues that the residual application of European Law in these three contested territories is strictly linked to the role of the EU as a peacekeeper. The paper concludes with the implications of the Protocols' enforcement on European differentiated disintegration.

2. Theoretical Framework: EU Differentiated Integration vs. Differentiated Disintegration

It is essential to start with a brief clarification of the theoretical framework. What is differentiated integration? What are its modes? How does it differ from differentiated disintegration? These questions are the object of this section. In 1996, Alex Stubb categorized differentiated integration.³ When examine the different concepts of differentiated integration, he says, it is important to distinguish between form and substance.⁴ For instance, multi-speed, variable geometry and *à la carte*, express different ways of differentiated integration, but difference in the substance. They are examples of differentiation in time, space and issue. Multi-speed integration EU is an example of differentiated integration in time. In this case, there are common objectives of integration, shared and driven by a core group of Member States, but pursued in different time. Variable geometry EU is a form of differentiation in space, which allows different levels of integration among Member States. Europe *à la carte* is the classic example of differentiation in matter, allowing Member States to choose policy areas of integration. This categorization is not entirely exhaustive, but it gives an idea of three different ways to pursue differentiated integration. From a constitutional perspective, differentiation has been analyzed as a process of differentiated integration. This phenomenon may as a combination of factor, such as the spread of Euroscepticism, or in nationalist Member States, willing to protect their sovereignty, or simply in wealthy Member States with a strong national identity. Being part of the EU, these State have institutional bargain power and are most likely to satisfy their demand for differentiated integration. As we will see in the next section, this negotiating power decreases if the State exits the EU, as it switches from a position of power to a position of demand.

According to Bruno De Witte, the existence of a controlled system of differentiation became a structural characteristic of the EU legal order.⁵ The functional reason is that it has proved essential for European integration. However, he had also noticed that the recourse to variable geometry was getting easy and accompanied by constitutional challenges such as lack of transparency, accountability, and a neglect of intra-state solidarity.⁶ De Witte underlined how the mechanism of

³ Alex Stubb, 'A Categorization of Differentiated Disintegration' (1996) 34(2) *Journal of Common Market Studies* 283

⁴ *Ibidem*.

⁵ Bruno De Witte, 'Variable Geometry and Differentiation as Structural Features of the EU Legal Order' in Bruno De Witte, Andrea Ott and Ellen Vos (eds), *Between Flexibility and Disintegration: The Trajectory of Differentiation in EU Law* (Edward Elgar 2017) 9–27.

⁶ *Ibidem*.

flexibility could have contributed to EU disintegration. This ‘prophecy’ perfectly fits the case of the UK’s membership in the EU, as we will see in the next section. The line between integration and disintegration seems blur. The question to be answered remains: what is the difference between differentiated integration and differentiated disintegration? In a static perspective differentiated integration and disintegration are the same: EU Law provision is not applied uniformly across the Member States. In a dynamic perspective, differentiated integration moves towards the goal of harmonization, but not all the Member States participate, or not at the same time or in the same way. On the contrary, differentiated disintegration refers to a Member State lowering its level and scope of integration, such as diminishing the adherence to EU Law and policies. In other word, as dynamic concepts, integration represents an increase in the level and scope of EU membership, while disintegration represents a reduction of it. Differentiated differentiation can be internal or external. The United Kingdom became a unique and first example of differentiated disintegration in the history of the European Union. During the Brexit negotiations and transitional period, it was a case of internal differentiated disintegration, which turned into external differentiated disintegration after January 2020.

3. Beyond Nationalism: British Euroscepticism

This article argues that Brexit is a process of progressive differentiation, from integration to disintegration. However, before going in depth with how differentiation has been used during the UK’s membership in the European Union, it is necessary to frame the bigger picture. This section disentangles the sources that led to the Brexit process. It provides an overview of the peculiarities of the British Euroscepticism, and of the British society. Baker⁷ summarised the British post-war history in four stages of Euroscepticism. The first phase was the initial post-war until British membership in 1973. The second phase was short, and it lasted till the first referendum in 1975. The third period until 1988, and then from 1988 onwards. These four stages are important to grasp the development of Euroscepticism in the United Kingdom. Euroscepticism in the UK is not a simple ‘hostility towards the EU’. Stephen George broader vision defines it as ‘the opposition to the increasing power of the EU’.⁸ Euroscepticism has more dimensions than simple hostility towards the European project. For George, Euroscepticism is having doubts about the form integration is taking. It means being sceptical about the benefits and advisability of further European integration and being hostile to the whole project. Later on, the infamous Prime Minister Cameron Bloomberg Speech will be analysed. It falls within George’s concept of Euroscepticism. Cameron was doubting the form of European integration and the benefits for the United Kingdom, pointing at how the EU should have changed. Stephen George⁹ also argues that British Euroscepticism has been influenced by four prejudices: (1) hostility against France and Germany, (2) prejudices in favour of the Commonwealth, (3) an attachment to the idea of having a special relationship with the United States, (4) an attachment to the idea and values of a national parliamentary sovereignty. These prejudices might find their roots in the romanticized idea of the United Kingdom as a (former) great imperial power. This concept might as well justify the historical attachment to national sovereignty. However, in the Bloomberg Speech there is no reference to this sense of ‘grandeur’. The requests for more differentiation are justified by the simple

⁷ David Baker, Andrew Gamble, Nick Randall and David Seawright, ‘Euroscepticism in the British Party System: A Source of Fascination, Perplexity, and Sometimes Frustration’ in Aleks Szczerbiak and Paul Taggart (eds), *Opposing Europe? The Comparative Party Politics of Euroscepticism. Volume 1: Case Studies and Country Surveys* (OUP 2008) 93–116.

⁸ Stephen George, ‘Britain: Anatomy of a Eurosceptic State’ (2000) 22(1) *Journal of European Integration* 15–33.

⁹ *Ibidem*.

geographical position: Great Britain is an island. Later, it is argued that Northern Ireland was treated as a ‘blind spot’ since the beginning of the Brexit process. Kuisma and Donoghue affirm that Brexit was essentially a process by which the different facets of British Euroscepticism were able to merge and be packaged in a way that made a cross-party alliance on the issue possible.¹⁰ Initially, it was one of the biggest fears after the referendum, was the possible domino effect. There is no evidence that the UK’s withdrawal from the EU would inspire new forms of Euroscepticism. The peculiarities of British Euroscepticism, which triggered Brexit, are unlikely to be replicated in other European countries. However, Brexit might have legitimized Eurosceptics, especially the negative narrative around the Eurozone and the migration crisis. According to Kuisma and Donoghue, the real question is to understand if the forces that led to Brexit could have been symptoms of a larger process of European disintegration.¹¹ The crucial point expressed by the authors is the idea of the British imagined community. This idea reinforced Euroscepticism and the four prejudices before mentioned. It has never been an issue between leavers and remainers, British vs Europeans. The leavers pushed the idea of nationalism, hence the idea of ‘British people’. Benedict Anderson’s work on imaginary communities is a useful tool to grasp this concept.¹² There is a strong connection between the development of the modern nation-state and the notion of heritage.¹³ ‘Heritage’ is the container for a ‘unique Britishness’, part of the ‘belonging’ to a specific national identity and to ‘othering’. This is why many who voted for the UK’s departure from the EU hoped to regain control, regain what ‘once was.’ However, as the community is imagined, so is the history behind the heritage defended.¹⁴ The idea of a ‘imagined community’ is that what binds nations together is a constructed sense of identity. ‘Nationalism is not the awakening of nations to self-consciousness; it invents nations where do not exist’. The leavers were able to imagine a united British community and to provide it with a sense of uniqueness and supremacy, a sense of exceptionalism over other nations (or blocks). According to Anderson: ‘it is an imagined community’ since, regardless of the internal inequality, the nation is perceived as horizontal. In terms of the Leave campaign, a British identity was constructed. Those who supported the remain, and identify as European, are laying on a political identity, and are supporting mostly the benefits given by the EU, rather than their sense of Europeaness. It could be understood as being pro UK in the EU, rather than being in favour of European integration in general. According to Kuisma and Donoghue, the remainers position falls into the same trap, as it elevates the UK in a supreme and exceptional position within the EU. Both positions demonstrate a gap in the knowledge of the UK’s history, and especially its history in the EU.¹⁵ There are at least two considerations to make at this stage. On the one hand, the idea of benefitting from the EU, rather than supporting European integration, explains Cameron’s requests in the Bloomberg speech. He clearly stated he was questioning the shape of European integration, and he wanted to address the UK’s position in a practical manner. On the other hand, the constructed idea of a British society left behind Northern Ireland. In the Brexit discourse, Northern Ireland was treated as a blind spot. The practical issues regarding the border and peacekeeping and the respect of the Good Friday Agreement provisions came up only during the negotiations phase. It demonstrates that the idea of an imaginary

¹⁰ Mikko Kuisma and Matthew Donoghue, ‘Brexit as a Phenomenon’ in Benjamin Leruth, Stefan Gänzle and Jarle Trondal (eds), *The Routledge Handbook of Differentiation in the European Union* (Routledge 2022) 605–618.

¹¹ *Ibidem*.

¹² Benedict Anderson, *Imagined Communities: Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism* (Verso, London 1991).

¹³ John Pendlebury and Loes Veldpaus, ‘Heritage and Brexit’ (2018) 19(3) *Planning Theory and Practice* 448–453.

¹⁴ Mikko Kuisma and Matthew Donoghue, ‘Brexit as a Phenomenon’ in Benjamin Leruth, Stefan Gänzle and Jarle Trondal (eds), *The Routledge Handbook of Differentiation in the European Union* (Routledge 2022) 605–618.

¹⁵ *Ibidem*.

and superior British society shadowed even another Constituent country. Indeed, the legal solution was to keep Northern Ireland close to the EU, confirming that the application of EU Law is acceptable only when functional to a practical matter.

A critique that can be moved is that Brexit represents a rationalization and simplification of a complex series of social relations and events leading up to the referendum and the withdrawal from the EU. Moreover, Brexit is the representation of ideologically assumptions. For instance, the word stands for Britain only, not considering Northern Ireland as part of the leaving process. Among scholars Brexit remains a cause of effects, rather than an effect of causes.¹⁶ The question should not be whether Brexit, meant as UK's withdrawal from EU, can create the domino effect. The question should be: to what extent domestic politics can influence supranational politics? The scholarship has been focused on Brexit as an origin of crisis, rather than a symptom of deeper fractures.¹⁷ The current threat to the European integration is the constellation of policy decisions, and political and economic and social crises that contributed to the UK's withdrawal from the EU. It does not mean that leavers were against the EU, they were most likely using it as a container of internal problems. The issue is not the disintegration but what causes it. The following section goes in-depth into the use of differentiation in the United Kingdom's history in the EU, as it has been a feature of its membership. The point is the same but more in political and legal terms: the withdrawal was a process, and the disintegration resulted from progressive differentiation.

4. The UK's Membership in the EU: a History of Differentiation

Compared to other European countries, the United Kingdom has a special history which has influenced its relationship with the EU. The legacy of the British colonial empire has left a sense of 'grandeur' that has translated into a particular attachment to the concept of national sovereignty. Since the beginning of its membership, the UK has sought differentiated integration solutions to safeguard its sovereignty. This article reconstructs the UK's membership in the EU, describing it as a parabola from internal differentiated integration to external differentiated disintegration. As mentioned in the introduction, this article divides the UK's membership in three phases: internal differentiated integration (1973-2016); internal differentiated disintegration (2016-2020); external differentiated disintegration (2020-present). The first phase is described with two major moments: the UK's Accession to the EU and the opt-outs granted in the following years; PM Cameron negotiation for a 'New membership'. This section illustrates how legal differentiation has always characterized the United Kingdom's membership in the EU, and the progressive demand for further differentiation. The following section considers the second and the third phase. The article argues that the withdrawal negotiations and transitional period can be considered as internal differentiated disintegration. Finally, the post-Brexit era is addressed as the first unique example of European differentiated disintegration.

4.1. Internal Differentiated Integration: 1973-1997

The first phase of the British EU membership was characterized by economic concerns regarding the European integration project - political and social aspects which strengthened Euroscepticism - followed by opt-outs in four major policy areas – legal differentiation. In the early 1950s, France, West Germany, Italy, Belgium, Luxembourg and the Netherlands laid the foundations of what is now

¹⁶ *Ibidem.*

¹⁷ *Ibidem.*

the European Union. In 1952 with the European Community of Steel and Coal (ECSC) and in 1957 with the Treaty of Rome (European Economic Community – EEC). The United Kingdom did not take part into this wave of European integration which followed the end of the second world war. In the 1950s the United Kingdom still enjoyed trade connections with the Commonwealth countries, following the principle of ‘imperial preference’ declared in the 1932 Import Duties Act.¹⁸ The United Kingdom started thinking about joining the EEC in the late 1950s, due to the decline of its economic performances. A first application was made in 1960, vetoed by France the following year. French President De Gaulle expressed concerns about the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) which was a pillar for the French economy. According to President De Gaulle, the United Kingdom would not have followed the general EEC integration model, having different economic interests than the Six EEC countries.¹⁹ De Gaulle was afraid that letting the UK into the EEC might foster the Americanisation of Europe. He was in favour of further and deeper integration rather than EEC enlargement. The United Kingdom knocked at the EEC doors again in 1967. British Prime Minister Wilson (Labour Party) started again the negotiations, and on 11 May submitted the second application to join the EEC, accompanied by Ireland, Denmark and Norway. On 27 November 1967, French President De Gaulle vetoed the UK’s Accession to the EEC for the second time. His concerns did not change, despite PM Wilson attempt to ease the tension. The talk reopened only after the end of De Gaulle’s mandate. The United Kingdom finally joined the EEC on 1 January 1973, together with Ireland and Denmark. Immediately after, in 1975 the United Kingdom held a referendum asking whether it should stay in the European Community. 67% voted to stay. However, this first referendum shaped the British attitude towards the EU project. Foreign Secretary James Callaghan said the matter was treated as a ‘business transaction’.²⁰ The idea that pooling sovereignty to other European Member States was a utilitarian calculation of costs and benefits, was expressed in the referendum question. Indeed, it referred to the participation in the European Market: ‘Do you think that the UK should stay in the European Community (Common Market)?’. Glencross argues that British Euroscepticism was born on the concerns regarding the costs of European integration.²¹ Thus, the fact that the membership was questioned after only two years and as a ‘business matter’ is not surprising. The same attitude was shown during the 2016 referendum campaign but with a fundamental difference: the core argument of safeguarding British sovereignty, expressed by the infamous slogan ‘taking back control’, was accompanied by populist concerns about migration flows. From a legal perspective, the willingness to participate in the European integration project for the sole economic benefits was crystallized as opt-outs. During its membership, the United Kingdom obtained four opt-outs in the following areas: (a) Eurozone, (b) Schengen, (c) Justice and Home Affairs and (d) the European Charter of Fundamental Rights. In 1992 the Maastricht Treaty was concluded, and the United Kingdom was granted an opt-out clause. It was not required to participate in the third stage of the European Monetary Union (EMU) integration, meaning staying outside the Eurozone. The conditions were specified in Protocol No 25 to the Maastricht Treaty.²² The Protocol No 25 states that the United

¹⁸ UK Parliament, ‘Into Europe’ (2016) <https://www.parliament.uk/about/living-heritage/transformingsociety/tradeindustry/importexport/overview/europe/> accessed [24 May 2025].

¹⁹ University of Luxembourg Centre for European History, ‘Historical Events in the European Integration’ <https://www.cvce.eu/en/education/unit-content/-/unit/02bb76df-d066-4c08-a58a-d4686a3e68ff/e491121c-8e37-473f-afe6-ff52e349c1aa> accessed [24 May 2025].

²⁰ Marlene Wind, ‘Brexit and Euroscepticism’ in Federico Fabbrini (ed), *The Law and Politics of Brexit* (OUP 2017).

²¹ Andrew Glencross, *Why the UK Voted for Brexit: David Cameron’s Great Miscalculation* (Palgrave Studies in European Union Politics 2016).

²² Protocol No 25 to the Maastricht Treaty on Certain Provisions Regarding the United Kingdom <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=legisum:l25060> accessed [24 May 2025].

Kingdom's powers in the field of monetary union policy are not affected by the Treaty; it is not subject to the provisions regarding excessive deficit; it is not concerned by the provisions regarding the European Central Bank or the European System of Central Banks or by the decisions taken by them. In addition, the United Kingdom announced the five economic tests which should have been met before moving towards the third stage of EMU integration. The five economic tests were based on: convergence of business cycles between the UK and the EU, flexibility, investment, financial services, growth, stability and jobs. Although the UK never joined the European Monetary Union, it is curious that it had established economic conditions additional to the Maastricht Treaty. The five economic test was performed in 2003, with a negative response.

The Schengen Treaty was signed on 14 June 1985, and it abolished border checks. The United Kingdom and Ireland never signed it, granting preference to the Common Travel Area between the two countries. When the Schengen Treaty was incorporated into the Amsterdam Treaty in 1997, the United Kingdom and Ireland were granted an opt-out for implementing it.²³ The Schengen Treaty provides that the UK – and Ireland – might request participation into some parts of it.²⁴ Despite the opt-out, the UK used the Schengen Information System, an intergovernmental database often used for law enforcement. In 1999 the UK had requested to participate in Title III of Schengen acquis regarding Police Security and Judicial Cooperation.²⁵

The UK's participation in EU legislation on Justice and Home Affairs (JHA) was regulated by Protocols 19 and 25 to the TEU and TFEU, the opt-out was originally granted with the Treaty of Amsterdam. Similarly to Schengen, the UK had the chance to opt-in for certain measures. The UK had to notify to the Council its intentions its intention to participated within three months of a proposal being presented, with no possibility of opting out later.²⁶ According to the Annual UK Government Report, the British Government recognized the benefits of the cooperation in JHA. However, it has always reserved the right to evaluate case by case.²⁷ The decision to opt-in was subject to both British Chambers' scrutiny before the Government could agree them in the Council. In particular, the decision was evaluated by the European Scrutiny Committee within the House of Commons, and by the European Union Committee within the House of Lords. This large margin of appreciation shows together with the control mechanism shows the strong willingness to keep sovereignty on Justice and Home Affairs. This issue will come back in the next section, namely in both the negotiations for a 'new membership' and later during the withdrawal negotiations.

Finally, the United Kingdom did not have a full opt-out from the European Charter of Fundamental Rights. Protocol No 30 to the Lisbon Treaty clarified the limits to its application in the UK.²⁸ In *NH vs Home Secretary*²⁹ the European Court of Justice itself never recognized a full disapplication, but

²³ Council Decision 2000/365/EC concerning the arrangements for the United Kingdom's participation in certain provisions of the Schengen acquis [2000] OJ L131/43.

²⁴ Art 4 of Protocol No 19 to the TEU and TFEU on the Schengen acquis.

²⁵ Council Decision 2000/365/EC concerning the arrangements for the United Kingdom's participation in certain provisions of the Schengen acquis [2000] OJ L131/43.

²⁶ Protocol (No 21) on the Position of the United Kingdom and Ireland in respect of the Area of Freedom, Security and Justice [2007] OJ C306/156.

²⁷ UK Government, 'JHA opt-in and Schengen opt-out Protocols' <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/jha-opt-in-and-schengen-opt-out-protocols--3> accessed [24 May 2025].

²⁸ Protocol No 30 to the Lisbon Treaty on the Application of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union to Poland and the United Kingdom <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:12008E%2FPRO%2F30> accessed [24 May 2025].

²⁹ *NH v Home Secretary* (Case C-411/10) EU:C:2011:514 <https://curia.europa.eu/juris/liste.jsf?num=C-411/10> accessed [24 May 2025].

a reduction of scope regarding certain areas, especially social rights.³⁰ Indeed, Art. 1 (2) of Protocol No specified that: *'Nothing in Title IV of the Charter creates justiciable rights applicable to the United Kingdom except in so far as the United Kingdom has provided for such rights in its national law.'*

In 1992 the UK had been granted an opt-out from the Social Pillar of the Maastricht Treaty. The Blair Government abolished it in 1997, as part of the Amsterdam Treaty. From this brief reconstruction it appears that the enforcement of social rights was considered in economic terms, as a possible burden for the UK. Despite the extensive opt-outs in major policy areas, in 2013 the United Kingdom evaluated again the cost and benefits of being part of the European Union. The issue of 'taking back control' became central in the national politics. In the public debate, the belonging to the European project was presented as a source of bureaucracy and expenditure for the State and the jurisdiction of the European Court of Justice was a constraint. The United Kingdom demanded further differentiation, leading PM Cameron to negotiate a 'new membership'.

4.2. Deepening Internal Differentiated Integration: 2013-2016

On 23 January 2013 Prime Minister Cameron gave the infamous Bloomberg speech.³¹ This speech could be considered the beginning of the disintegration phase. Even though the intention at the time was to negotiate further differentiation, not leaving, the Bloomberg speech led to the negotiations for a new membership and later to the Brexit referendum. It could be also considered the first major Euroskeptic speech, since Margaret Thatcher's Bruges speech in 1988.³² Prime Minister Cameron addresses the issue of how to change the EU to ensure prosperity. He confirms that the United Kingdom has always had a practical vision of the EU, as source of prosperity, stability, freedom and democracy. He said that the United Kingdom has been 'passionate in defence sovereignty' as 'our geography has shaped our psychology'. He justifies this position as the UK is an island, so with geography rather than mentioning the colonial and imperialist history. At the time, PM Cameron specified that *'the UK was committed to play an active part'* in the EU. He isolated three major challenges: the Eurozone, European competitiveness and the gap between EU and its citizens. If those challenges were not going to be addressed, the risk was that British citizens would drift towards the exit. Cameron expressed concerned about areas in which the UK opted out, like Eurozone, or was always careful to maintain sovereignty. At this stage, Prime Minister Cameron wished for relations with the EU with the UK in it. He affirmed five principles for the 21st century European Union. Among these he stressed the importance of flexibility, and he mentioned the countries who were not part of the Eurozone or Schengen. In other words, he presented differentiation to move forward. He supported the idea of a flexible Europe, where *'power must be able to flow back to the Member States'*. The Single Market does not need a full harmonization to function, according to Cameron. Moreover, he mentioned that national parliaments should have a bigger role to ensure democratic accountability. *'Our participation in the single market, and our ability to help set its rules is the principal reason for our membership of the EU. So it is a vital interest for us to protect the integrity*

³⁰ British Institute of International and Comparative Law, 'FAQ – Brexit and the Charter – Part One' [https://www.biiicl.org/documents/1950_faq_-_brexit_and_the_charter_-_part_one.pdf?showdocument=1#:~:text=The%20Court%20of%20Justice%20of,%20\(at%20para%203.6\)](https://www.biiicl.org/documents/1950_faq_-_brexit_and_the_charter_-_part_one.pdf?showdocument=1#:~:text=The%20Court%20of%20Justice%20of,%20(at%20para%203.6)) accessed [24 May 2025].

³¹ UK Government, 'Prime Minister Cameron Discussed the Future of the European Union at Bloomberg' (23 January 2013) <https://www.gov.uk/government/speeches/eu-speech-at-bloomberg> accessed [24 May 2025].

³² Margaret Thatcher Foundation, 'Speech to the College of Europe' (20 September 1988) <https://www.margaretthatcher.org/document%2F107332> accessed [24 May 2025].

*and fairness of the single market for all its members.*³³ He reasserted that British people voted to enter a common market, and that was all they wanted. In this speech, there are the root of the ‘take back control’ slogan, and especially referring to the European Court of Justice jurisdiction. PM Cameron mentioned that British citizens were afraid that come ECJ’s judgement impact life in Britain. Overall, he questions Britain’s position in the EU. And while it is sure that he used ‘Britain’ as synecdoche, it also shows no mention for Northern Ireland. Finally, he was in favor of an in-out referendum, however, saying that it would not have been a wise choice at the time. He opened the doors to negotiate a new settlement.

Following the outcome of the 2015 general elections, Prime Minister David Cameron sent a letter to the European Council President Donald Tusk with a series of proposals in four major areas: economic governance, sovereignty, competitiveness and immigration. A draft agreement circulated among the Member States.³⁴ The agreement was reached at the European Council in February 2016. It envisaged conditions regarding the economic governance, mutual respect, and loyal cooperation. They would have been ensured among Member States participating or not participating in the Eurozone. The Union's banking union regulations apply only to credit institutions located in Member States whose currency is the euro or which have concluded a close cooperation agreement with the European Central Bank regarding prudential supervision. Regarding competition, the EU was committed to increasing competitiveness by strengthening the internal market and adapting it to keep pace with the changing international environment. EU and Member State institutions were committed to legislating to achieve these goals. On immigration, the British government had obtained a so-called ‘emergency brake’ that could have been activated for seven years. This tool would have made it possible not to extend welfare benefits to all newcomer workers. Finally, on sovereignty, it was recognized that the UK was not obliged to further political integration into the EU. The UK would no longer be obliged to an ‘ever-closer Union.’ The role of national parliaments in EU law-making and decision-making was also emphasized. This agreement would have come into force if the United Kingdom had decided to stay in the EU on 23 June 2016. Despite Prime Minister Cameron's achievement, 51.9 percent of voters chose to leave the EU. The referendum result opened the phase of differentiated disintegration of the United Kingdom into the European Union.

4.3. From Internal to External Differentiated Disintegration

As mentioned, this article argues that the disintegration phase started in the immediate aftermath of the referendum. This phase moved from internal to external disintegration as the United Kingdom was still a Member State while negotiating the withdrawal and during the transition period. This argument is based on both legal and political considerations. On the one hand, the intention to leave was clear with the activation of the Art. 50 TEU. The United Kingdom did not revoke the withdrawal notification, even if the European Court of Justice offered this opportunity in December 2018, with the *Wightman* judgement.³⁵ Moreover, the delays granted by the European Union served the purpose of avoiding a ‘no-deal Brexit.’ On the other hand, the political discourse left no room for misunderstanding. Prime Minister May and Johnson wanted to lead the country out of the EU, despite the uncertainties on how to withdraw and on Northern Ireland; in their words, there never was a hint

³³ UK Government, ‘Prime Minister Cameron Discussed the Future of the European Union at Bloomberg’ (23 January 2013) <https://www.gov.uk/government/speeches/eu-speech-at-bloomberg> accessed [24 May 2025].

³⁴ POLITICO, ‘David Cameron’s EU Reform Deal Scorecard: What He Asked, What He Got, and What It Means’ <https://www.politico.eu/article/david-cameron-eu-reform-deal-scorecard-brexiteu-referendum-agreement/> accessed [24 May 2025].

³⁵ *Wightman and Others v Secretary of State for Exiting the European Union* (Case C-621/18) EU:C:2018:999.

of hesitation. In this section, the Brexit phenomenon is analysed as a unique case of European differentiated disintegration, considering the negotiation phase. It explains what the UK lost and how its position in the EU changed when it began negotiating the withdrawal.

Brexit is a first case of European differentiated disintegration. From a static perspective differentiated integration and differentiated disintegration are the same. European Union Law is not applied uniformly. In the case of internal differentiation Member States are excluded from applying certain rules; in the case of external differentiation other actors are exempted. However, they differ in a dynamic perspective.³⁶ Differentiated integration refers to a situation in which integration progress but at least one actor remains at the status quo or does not participate in the same level as the others.³⁷ It was the case for the United Kingdom, enjoying opt-outs in four major areas. Differentiated disintegration is the selective reduction of a state's adherence to the shared legal provisions, whereas the other actors remain at the same level of harmonization.³⁸ Frank Schimmelfennig argues that differentiated integration and disintegration differ in the negotiation structure when it comes to the institutional bargain power. The UK has been known historically for his constitutional differentiation. It has shown concern in defending national sovereignty and identity, instead of deepening European integration. The United Kingdom tried to keep power into the 'core state powers', namely the areas of army, police and justice system, currency and public administration.³⁹ When the European Union expanded its competence into those area, the United Kingdom negotiated a broad set of exceptions, such as a Schengen-free travel regime, selective participation into Justice and Home Affairs, opt-out from the monetary Union, the social chapter of the Maastricht Treaty and Charter of Fundamental Rights. These arrangements were possible, as the United Kingdom was part of the European Union, and it could exercise its bargain power within the European institutions. The constant demand for further disintegration was based on the negotiation power that the United Kingdom used to have, as a Member State. However, after Brexit, it turned into a third state demanding differentiated disintegration. Its position shifted, from a country with institutional bargain power to a country in a demanding position.⁴⁰ In the first case, the United Kingdom was a country defending the *status quo*. Eurosceptics Member States are considered *status quo* oriented, and they can use their veto to block further European integration. This is the source of their institutional bargain power: with their veto they can prevent Treaty reforms. Even the threat of using the veto can serve to negotiate further opt-outs. The European institutions are weaker when Eurosceptic Member States negotiate differentiation. This is the reason why differentiated integration is tolerated as long as integration proceeds in the EU. As the first part of this analysis shows, it has been a regulatory tool in the EU, often used by the United Kingdom. The Bloomberg Speech is a good example. On the contrary, demanding differentiated disintegration, goes against the EU principles, such as the 'even closer Europe'. Negotiating differentiation from the outside, as a third state, makes the other EU Member States the advocates of the *status quo*. After Brexit, the United Kingdom insistence on disintegration was a not such a strong threat for the European Union. The UK market and economy alone are weaker,

³⁶ Frank Schimmelfennig, '(Post-) Brexit: Negotiating Differentiated Disintegration in the European Union' in Benjamin Leruth, Stefan Gänzle and Jarle Trondal (eds), *The Routledge Handbook of Differentiation in the European Union* (Routledge 2022) 619–635.

³⁷ *Ibidem*.

³⁸ *Ibidem*.

³⁹ Philipp Genschel and Markus Jachtenfuchs, *Beyond the Regulatory Polity? The European Integration of Core State Powers* (Oxford University Press 2014).

⁴⁰ Frank Schimmelfennig, '(Post-) Brexit: Negotiating Differentiated Disintegration in the European Union' in Benjamin Leruth, Stefan Gänzle and Jarle Trondal (eds), *The Routledge Handbook of Differentiation in the European Union* (Routledge 2022) 619–635.

despite the threat of bilateral trade agreements and stronger transatlantic relations. In this specific case, it is one country and one market against twenty-seven. Moreover, the desire for differentiated disintegration is often driven by nationalist or populist ideas rather than economic interests. It surely was the case for Brexit, as the Leave campaign focused mostly on sovereignty and identity, as well as immigration issues, without considering the economic consequences. Indeed, the United Kingdom lost negotiation power. A demonstration of this concept advocated by Schimmelfennig is the Northern Ireland Protocol. No significant changes were made in favor of the UK's demands at the negotiation stage. The Northern Ireland Protocol, which the Prime Minister failed to get the British Parliament to vote for, does not differ much from the one subsequently approved during the Johnson administration. Northern Ireland remains in the British market *de jure* but is, in fact, in the EU customs union, at least as far as goods moving from Britain to the island of Ireland are concerned. Finding itself at a negotiating disadvantage and risking a 'no-deal' Brexit, the UK has moved the invisible border into the Irish Sea. The Windsor Framework did not alter its substance even after the Northern Ireland Protocol came into force. It merely improved some technical aspects of the trade flow from Great Britain to the island of Ireland. According to Dagmar Schiek,⁴¹ this would be a different understanding of the concept of negotiation. Once a treaty is approved, the European Union moves to the implementation stage. The UK wished to continue negotiations thereafter.

Applying Schimmelfennig theory to the events, the decision to link the negotiations for a 'new membership' to an in-out referendum had two advantages. On the one hand, the threat of a referendum to leave the EU was used to gain more concessions from the other Member States; on the other hand, extracting concession from the Member States served to moderate Eurosceptics to vote to remain.⁴² The credibility of the referendum threat was low at the time. It was in both Cameron's and the EU's interest that the UK stayed in the European Union, and nobody expected a negative referendum outcome in any case. The negotiations consolidated the differentiated integration, without substantial alteration. The result of the referendum was surprising. After PM Cameron was forced out of office, and new PM Theresa May was called to lead the UK out of the EU, it became quite clear that the British politics were not prepared. Not only they did not anticipate the result of the referendum, but they did not expect the shift in terms of negotiation power. After decades of differentiation, obtain thanks to a strong bargain power, the United Kingdom found itself in a weaker demanding position. In negotiation terms, the options were 'soft Brexit' - with the UK keeping the EU internal market or a custom union - or 'hard Brexit' - free-trade agreement - without a clear vision for the withdrawal and for the future relations. This was particularly clear when the UK asked the extensions, to avoid the so called 'no-deal Brexit', which would have happened under Art. 50 TEU if no agreement was signed. In January 2017, May opted for an 'hard Brexit' in her Lancaster House Speech,⁴³ confirmed in her withdrawal letter to the EU. The reason behind this decision was to leave the EU legislation and the jurisdiction of the Court of Justice of the EU (CJEU). As explained in the following section, the United Kingdom did not achieve this goal entirely. The article illustrates how and why a residual extraterritorial application of European Union Law survived. In the withdrawing phase, the EU

⁴¹ Dagmar Schiek, 'Brexit and the Implementation of the Withdrawal Agreement' in Federico Fabbrini (ed), *The Law and Politics of Brexit, Volume II* (OUP 2021) 49–70.

⁴² Frank Schimmelfennig, '(Post-) Brexit: Negotiating Differentiated Disintegration in the European Union' in Benjamin Leruth, Stefan Gänzle and Jarle Trondal (eds), *The Routledge Handbook of Differentiation in the European Union* (Routledge 2022) 619–635.

⁴³ UK Government, 'The Government's Negotiating Objectives for Exiting the EU: PM Speech' <https://www.gov.uk/government/speeches/the-governments-negotiating-objectives-for-exiting-the-eu-pm-speech> accessed [24 May 2025].

pursued three goals: protecting EU citizens' rights in the UK, a 'single financial settlement', avoiding an 'hard-border' within the island of Ireland. During the transition period the United Kingdom had all the legal rights and obligations of a Member State but participation in decision-making.⁴⁴ Hence, this article argues that disintegration had started, even if it was internal at the time. In 2019, Prime Minister May failed three times to obtain a majority for the withdrawal agreement in the House of Commons. Her successor Boris Johnson accepted the main provisions of the withdrawal agreement, to avoid a 'no-deal Brexit', despite his original hardline position. The withdrawal agreement entered into force on 31 January 2020. Differentiated disintegration became external. Differentiated disintegration introduces to the politics of differentiation in the European Union a change in negotiations structure resulting in a reversal of bargain power.⁴⁵ In these negotiations, the EU enjoyed the superior institutional power produced by starkly asymmetrical economic interdependence, the coherence and the unity bestowed by a common interest in avoiding 'cherry-picking'.⁴⁶ Economic interest runs against differentiated disintegration. Even if Brexit is not likely to have a domino effect, its process might affect future negotiations for differentiation.

The following section goes into depth into the current phase of the post-Brexit era: enforcement of residual EU Law. It disentangles how some provisions of European Union Law survived, despite the UK's effort to negotiate disintegration.

5. Extraterritorial Application of EU Law in Northern Ireland, Gibraltar and Cyprus

The final section of the article focuses on what survived the disintegration phase, particularly the rules of European Union law that apply in Northern Ireland, Gibraltar, and the Sovereign Base Areas in Cyprus. These are three cases of residual and extraterritorial application of EU law. The *raison d'être* of this legislative choice is the history of these contested territories. The article argues that these rules of European law escaped the disintegration sought by the United Kingdom for a particular reason: the European Union's function as a peacekeeper. Indeed, beyond the practical reasons related to the geographical characteristics of the three territories, EU law, in this case, serves to maintain peace and stability.

The most controversial case is certainly Northern Ireland. As noticed, it received no particular concern during the referendum campaign. However, immediately after the result, it was clear the issue of a land border would have been central in the negotiations. A hard border between Ireland and Northern Ireland would have caused both economic and political consequences. On the one hand it would have resulted in disruption of the cross-border movement of goods and supply-chain. On the other hand, the 1998 Good Friday Agreement made the border invisible thanks to a de-militarization and de-securitizing process, as a symbol of peacekeeping and political stability. The Good Friday Agreement does not contain many references to the EU. However, the fact that both the United Kingdom and Ireland joined the EU at the same time and shared the single market, avoided the definition of a hard border. An actual physical border would have reminisced the painful memories of the times of conflict in the island.⁴⁷ The return of any infrastructure would have been seen as a reversal of the positive developments of the past twenty years. Indeed, the creation of a custom border was at the centre of the Brexit negotiations. Border communities campaigned against a physical border, as it could have turned into an easy target for terrorist attacks. For all these reasons the UK

⁴⁴ *Ibidem*.

⁴⁵ *Ibidem*.

⁴⁶ *Ibidem*.

⁴⁷ Dagmar Schiek, 'The Island of Ireland and Brexit' (2018) 69 *Northern Ireland Legal Quarterly* 387–407.

negotiated a regional differentiated Brexit for Northern Ireland. The need for differentiation was expressed in August 2016 by First Minister Arlene Foster and the deputy First Minister Martin McGuinness.⁴⁸ They issued a joint statement arguing that the withdrawal should have considered Northern Ireland as the only region sharing a land border with the EU. In October 2016, members of the Northern Ireland assembly debated a ‘special status’ for Northern Ireland.⁴⁹ The motion was supported by the Alliance and by the two nationalist parties, Sinn Féin and the Social Democratic and Labour Party (SDLP). It was opposed by the Democratic Unionist Party (DUP) and the Ulster Unionist Party (UUP). Arlene Foster, DUP leader, was in favour of a special status for Northern Ireland, but the party opposed any solution that could have undermined its position in the UK. The DUP clearly had a strong ideological position, that did not consider the economic consequences of Brexit in Northern Ireland.⁵⁰ Theresa May supported the withdrawal of the United Kingdom as a whole, but she was still recognising the unique position of Northern Ireland and the concern expressed by Foster and McGuinness.⁵¹ The House of Lords, from his side, said that all parties in the Brexit negotiations should recognize the ‘special and unique nature of the UK-Irish relations, and the position of Northern Ireland’.⁵² On 20 March 2017, the UK government formally notified the withdrawal to the European Council. Prime Minister May stressed the importance of the peace process in Northern Ireland, the need to avoid a hard border, and the unique relations with Ireland. The Good Friday Agreement needed to be preserved, even though the British government was silent on how to achieve this goal. The European Council adopted withdrawal negotiations guidelines in April 2017.⁵³ The European Council remarked the need to preserve the Good Friday Agreement and the peace process in Northern Ireland. It recognized ‘the unique circumstances on the island of Ireland’ and that ‘flexible, imaginative solutions’ were required.⁵⁴ However, no concrete solutions or answers were proposed. In February 2018 the European Commission drafted the text of the Withdrawal Agreement, including a Protocol on Ireland/Northern Ireland. It envisaged the idea of the ‘backstop’ Protocol. Northern Ireland would have maintained the EU customs territory. The effect would be freedom of movement of goods on the island of Ireland, but no freedom of movement of persons and services was included. This solution avoided a hard border on the island, providing Northern Ireland’s participation in the EU internal market. The consequence was that Northern Ireland would have been treated differently than the rest of the UK.⁵⁵ This solution was refused by the Unionists as it could threaten the unity of the UK internal market, and it could have driven Northern Ireland away from the rest of Britain. Theresa May said that ‘no UK prime minister could ever agree to it’.⁵⁶ The arrangements would undermine the UK common market and threaten the UK constitutional integrity. Catherine Barnard argues that the concept of UK internal market unity came up only after Brexit.⁵⁷ It was never relevant before the withdrawal from the EU. Negotiations continued in 2018, until an agreement was reached. It included

⁴⁸ The Executive Office Northern Ireland, ‘Letter to the Prime Minister Rt Hon Theresa May MP’ <https://www.executiveoffice-ni.gov.uk/publications/letter-prime-minister-rt-hon-theresa-may-mp> accessed [24 May 2025].

⁴⁹ Northern Ireland Assembly, ‘Minutes of Proceedings: Monday 17 October 2016’ <https://www.niassembly.gov.uk/assembly-business/minutes-of-proceedings/session-2016-2017/monday-17-october-2016/> accessed [24 May 2025].

⁵⁰ David Phinnemore, ‘Brexit and Northern Ireland’ in Benjamin Leruth, Stefan Gänzle and Jarle Trondal (eds), *The Routledge Handbook of Differentiation in the European Union* (Routledge 2022) 636–648.

⁵¹ *Ibidem*.

⁵² House of Lords European Union Committee, *Brexit: UK–Irish Relations* (6th Report of Session 2016–17, HL Paper 76) <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/ld201617/ldselect/lducom/76/7602.htm> accessed [24 May 2025].

⁵³ European Council, ‘European Council (Art. 50) Guidelines for Brexit Negotiations’ (29 April 2017) <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2017/04/29/euco-brexit-guidelines/> accessed [24 May 2025].

⁵⁴ *Ibidem*.

⁵⁵ Phinnemore (2022).

⁵⁶ *Ibidem*.

⁵⁷ Catherine Barnard, ‘The UK Internal Market’ in Federico Fabbrini (ed), *The Law and Politics of Brexit* (OUP 2017) 173–194.

some ‘backstop’ provisions, including Northern Ireland in regulatory alignment with the EU. The ‘common regulatory area’ was dropped in theory, but it remained the same in practice. The rest of the UK would be in a customs union with the EU. This last provision costed Prime minister May three negative consecutive votes within the British Parliament. On the one hand, members of the DUP, essential for May to achieve majority in the domestic parliament, voted against it, but as Northern Ireland would also have been treated differently. On the other hand, keeping a customs union with the EU was contrary to the reasons that inspired Brexit in the first place. Theresa May resigned in July 2019. She was succeeded by Boris Johnson, who promised to ‘ditch the backstop’.⁵⁸ The idea of the UK in a customs Union with the EU was abandoned. However, the revised Northern Ireland Protocol of October 2019 ensured a differentiated treatment for Northern Ireland. In December 2019 the British parliament approved the Withdrawal Agreement which entered into force on the 31 January 2020. The Protocol on Northern Ireland entered into force on 1 January 2021. Like extensively explained in this thesis, Northern Ireland remained *de facto* in the UK internal market (Art. 6 of the Northern Ireland Protocol). However, it is *de jure* part of the EU Customs Union (Art. 5 of the Northern Ireland Protocol), as the Union Customs Code applies in respect of Northern Ireland. Northern Ireland is not part of the EU Common Commercial Policy, so it does not access to trade preferences contained in EU third-country agreements.

The negotiations of the Gibraltar and Cyprus Protocols took a different course. In the case of Gibraltar, being an Oversea Territory joined the EU at the same time as the rest of the United Kingdom. It enjoyed some opt-outs as it was left outside the Customs Union and the VAT area, and it was excluded from the Common Agricultural Policy. Even if, in theory, there was no danger to create a new customs border, the past tensions with Spain came up. Indeed, the political tension caused by the Spanish claim affected the Protocol during the negotiations and it is still affecting the enforcement. The Protocol negotiated a regional differentiated solution, but it left many uncertainties. Regarding the freedom of movement of persons, Gibraltar should acquire the status of Schengen free-passport area. However, this solution was never fully enforced. There has been disagreement over who should carry out the checks at the crossing points. As part of the Schengen areas, Spain should be responsible for the application of the Schengen Borders Code. Gibraltar will also check if a traveller is allowed to enter its territory. This hybrid system should prevent Gibraltar from being an unguarded gate to the Schengen area. Regarding the movement of goods, there are some similarities with the Northern Ireland Protocol. The aim of the Gibraltar Protocol is to remove the physical barriers between Gibraltar and the EU. EU customs, excise and VAT legislation will be applied extraterritorially.

In the case of Cyprus, the UK’s Sovereign Base Areas enjoy an exceptional status under EU Law. The territorial differentiated solution negotiated for the UK’s SBAs in Cyprus relies on maintaining the *status quo*. The *raison d’être* of the Withdrawal Agreement Cyprus Protocol is the continuity of the exceptional regime of the SBAs under EU Law. They were part of the EU customs Union since 1 May 2004, when Cyprus joined the EU and as specified in Protocol No 3. Indeed, the negotiations went smoothly as Protocol No 3 to the Accession Treaty was basically reproduced in the Protocol attached to the Withdrawal Agreement. Article 2 of the Cyprus Protocol keeps the Sovereign Base Areas in the EU customs territory. They are officially in the list of third countries being part of the EU customs territory. The checks are carried out by the Republic of Cyprus except for goods concerning the military activity of the SBAs. Moreover, the reproduction of Protocol No 3 spared the

⁵⁸ Phinnemore (2022).

United Kingdom the violation of the Treaty of Establishment. Indeed, the United Kingdom is a Guarantor of the Cyprus Republic and independence. Under the Treaty of Establishment, the United Kingdom has an obligation to refrain from creating custom posts on the island. The preservation of Protocol No 3 and its partial reproduction into the Withdrawal Agreement Protocol spared Cyprus the same social and political frictions that Northern Ireland experienced during the Brexit negotiations. Concerning the movement of persons, the United Kingdom exercises the control on persons crossing the external boundaries of the SBAs, meaning the border with the internationally unrecognized Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus. In this case, a third country – the UK – is responsible for enforcing EU Law measures. The UK authorities are in cooperation with the Cypriot authorities, contrary to the situation in Gibraltar.

The question to be answered is: why some provisions of EU Law survived in these three Protocols? The solution negotiated for these three territories was the extraterritorial application of EU Law. The regional differentiated application of EU Law has two main reasons in these three territories: safeguarding the constitutional status deriving from the conflicts experienced, and the role of the European Union as peacekeeper. The Withdrawal Agreement Protocols aim to create continuity with the territories former EU legal status. The Protocols attached to the Withdrawal Agreement exist as these territories experienced a conflict (or a claim). Concerning the role of the European Union in the peace process, the EU is not an initiator of peace-making itself. However, it is often an added value to make conflict resolution quicker.⁵⁹ The EU is better equipped to carry conflict resolution before the state access the EU, rather than after. This aspect is particularly visible in Cyprus, where talks about peace have been in a stall since its accession to the EU. After the failure of the Annan Plan V, there has been no other concrete proposal for peace. This contradiction is defined as ‘the paradox of the Europeanisation of intrastate conflicts’.⁶⁰ After the accession of any candidate state, the Union tends to accommodate the conflict within its political and legal order. Brexit offers a unique opportunity to understand how the detachment of a state from the EU structures affects border conflicts and what are the mechanisms that can be used to manage those tensions. Skoutaris thinks of territorial differentiation as a tool that has been used in the Brexit negotiation to address the tensions created in Northern Ireland, Gibraltar and Cyprus.⁶¹ The UK and the EU have extended the application of EU Law outside the Union’s territory, to keep the status quo – hence peace and stability – in the three contested territories. The link with the UK and the constitutional status of the three territories influenced the way EU Law was applied when the UK was still a Member State. For the same reason, it influences the way Brexit was negotiated, and legislation was adopted. It influences the way as well Brexit is enforced. Brexit threatened the balance in those territories, and the role of the EU as peacekeeper. Translating the campaign slogan ‘Take back control’ in legal terms, means ‘Stop applying EU Law’. However, the presence of the European Union served to keep stability, and the application of EU Law preserved those areas’ economic interests. The decision of leaving the single market might work for the United Kingdom, but it did not work for territories that share a border with the EU, or which are a Member State like Cyprus. Hence, extraterritorial application of EU Law seems like an appropriate legal solution.

⁵⁹ Nikos Skoutaris, ‘Border Conflicts after Brexit’ in Benjamin Leruth, Stefan Gänzle and Jarle Trondal (eds), *The Routledge Handbook of Differentiation in the European Union* (Routledge 2022) 649–662.

⁶⁰ *Ibidem*.

⁶¹ *Ibidem*.

6. Conclusions

Brexit is the first case of European Differentiated Disintegration. For the first time in the history of the European Union, a (former) Member State decided to seek a level of flexibility never explored before. To fully grasp to what extent differentiation has been used, and for what scope, Brexit should be seen as a process. The United Kingdom is not ‘the awkward neighbour’, but a former Member State respecting a democratic referendum, coherent with its differentiation history. This article argues that the UK’s membership in the EU could be seen as a parabola from internal differentiated integration to external differentiated disintegration. Contrary to other scholars, this thesis argues that the disintegration phase started before the actual departure from the EU. As the United Kingdom was formally a Member State during the negotiations and the transition period, the disintegration was internal. After Art. 50 TEU was activated, the political discourse indicated clearly the intentions to leave. PM May and Johnson never showed second thoughts. Neither did Northern Ireland Prime Minister Foster and Vice PM McGuinness, despite the delicate situation in their country or the fact that NI voted to stay in the EU. Moreover, the European Court of Justice stated the possibility to revoke the withdrawal notification with the *Wightman* judgement in December 2018. The United Kingdom never look back.

The second main argument of this article evolves around the concept of ‘multiple Brexit’ and the use of regional differentiation and extraterritorial application of EU Law. This process had a different impact on Northern Ireland, Gibraltar and Cyprus. Regional differentiation is not a novelty for European Law. Neither is the extraterritorial application of EU Law. However, it is the first case of European Disintegration involving three contested territories. Differentiated Brexit is a solution that reflects the needs and specificities of the territories involved, especially in the case of the three contested regions of Northern Ireland, Gibraltar and Cyprus. The extraterritorial application of EU Law is the legal tool that the parties found appropriate to avoid breaking international law and previous international treaties – such as the Good Friday Agreement or the Treaty of Establishment – and to keep peace and balance in fragile situations. New borders were born, in three territories already affected by recent conflicts, claims, or partially occupied. Differentiated solutions for these territories are not justified by geography alone – e.g. extraterritorial application of EU Law applies for remote islands like the French Overseas Territories. Differentiation was needed due to fragile political situation linked to the past conflicts or claim, and to the constitutional status in the United Kingdom. From the United Kingdom perspective, differentiation in Gibraltar and Cyprus was not considered a threat for the UK’s constitutional integrity, as they have a more distant constitutional status than Northern Ireland. It is easier to justify differentiated relations for an overseas territory with a high level of autonomy – Gibraltar- or to simply confirm the previous level of differentiation – like in the SBAs in Cyprus. However, the issue was raised in the case of Northern Ireland. The impact of these territorial differentiated solutions has certainly been stronger in Northern Ireland, being one of four constituent nations of the United Kingdom. It might be argued that differentiated Brexit reflects the results of the 2016 referendum vote. Scotland, Northern Ireland and Gibraltar voted to remain. Even if it is not part of this analysis, the Scottish government argued immediately in favor a differentiated solution, to keep Scotland closer to the EU. While a regional differentiated solution was rejected for Scotland, it was adopted for Northern Ireland, Gibraltar and the SBAs in Cyprus. This shows that leaving the European single market threatened the political and economic stability of the three territories. Moreover, it is not certain that during the referendum campaign, the supporters of ‘leave’ had considered the consequences for these three regions.

In conclusion, while David Phinnemore considers the three Protocols attached to the Withdrawal Agreement in contrast with the disintegration dynamic that the UK was seeking with Brexit, this article argues that they are coherent with the scope of peacekeeping. He affirms that while Brexit is an overall process of differentiated disintegration, there are portions of a former Member State that keep a different, higher level of integration. This is technically true. However, new forms of differentiated disintegration were adopted to address unique circumstances and find practical solutions. The extraterritorial application of EU Law in Northern Ireland, Gibraltar and Cyprus does not pursue the scope of integration with the European Union. The legal reasoning for this flexible and creative solution is the EU role as peacekeeper, and the need to maintain stability in these contested territories. Otherwise, why would a former Member State that wanted to ‘take back control’ would accept to apply European Union Law? The question to be answered is whether the differentiated arrangements envisaging the extraterritorial application of EU Law is sufficient to address the post-Brexit tension in the three contested territories. The Northern Ireland Protocol full operation is subject to a democratic consent vote potentially every four years. The Protocol could be politicized continuously, and this might affect its implementation, for better or worse. The Windsor Framework itself is first evidence that politicization of the Protocol might block its implementation or unblock it. In Gibraltar, the politics between the actors involved are blocking the Protocol enforcement. The preliminary conclusion is that in this case the differentiation has not worked – not yet. Finally, the differentiation in Cyprus is working as it reproduces the former legal status quo.